

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF METFORMIN
HYDROCHLORIDE AND GLICLAZIDE IN BULK AND
TABLET DOSAGE FORM BY RP-HPLC METHOD****Pasupuleti Maneesha Rani^{1*}, Pinnamaneni Prachet, Morla Siva Prasad,
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Chalapathi Nagar, Lam, Guntur 522034, Andhra Pradesh, India.**Article Received:** December 2019 **Accepted:** January 2020 **Published:** February 2020**Abstract:**

A simple, precise, rapid, selective, and economic reversed phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method has been established for the simultaneous analysis of Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate in Bulk and Pharmaceutical dosage form on a Phenomenex C₁₈ (250×4.6mm i.d) chromatographic column equilibrated with mobile phase containing methanol, acetonitrile & Phosphate buffer (2.954g of potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate in 1000 ml water). Experimental conditions such as pH of mobile phase, organic phase ratio, flow rate, selection of wavelength, etc. were critically studied and the optimum conditions were selected. Efficient chromatographic separation was achieved with mobile phase containing combination of methanol, acetonitrile & phosphate buffer pH 5.0 in ratio of 55:10:35 v/v and mixture was adjusted to pH 5.0 at flow rate of 1.5 ml/min and eluent was monitored at 257 nm. The sample was injected using a 20 µl fixed loop, and the total run time was 5 min. The retention time for Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate were 1.037 min and 2.123 min respectively. The method was linear in the range of 10-50 µg/ml and for both Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate. The proposed method was successfully applied to the analysis of Lamivudine & Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate in their Bulk and Pharmaceutical dosage form without interference from other additives. The developed method was validated according to ICH guidelines. Linearity, regression value, recovery, % RSD of method precision, LOD, LOQ values were found within the limits and the method was found to be satisfactory. This validated HPLC procedure is economic, sensitive, user-friendly & less time consuming than other chromatographic procedures.

Key words: RP-HPLC, Lamivudine, Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate, validation, chromatography.**Corresponding author:****Pasupuleti Maneesha Rani,**Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis,
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Please cite this article in press Pasupuleti Maneesha Rani et al, **Simultaneous Estimation Of Metformin Hydrochloride And Gliclazide In Bulk And Tablet Dosage Form By RP-HPLC Method.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(02).

INTRODUCTION:**Pharmaceutical Analysis & Quality Assurance**

Pharmaceutical analysis is a branch of practical chemistry that involves a series of method for identification, determination, quantification and purification of a substance, separation of the elements of an answer or mixture, or determination of structure of compound. The substance could also be one compound or a combination of compounds and it should be in any of the dosage form.

Quality assurance plays a central role in determining the safety and efficacy of medicines. Extremely specific and sensitive analytical techniques hold the key to the design, development, standardization and quality control of medicinal products. they are equally vital in material medical and in drug metabolism studies, both of that are basic to the assessment of bioavailability and the period of clinical response. However, modern ideas of quality differs and concerned not only with chemical purity, however additionally with those other characteristics of pharmaceutical materials which can influence safety , efficacy, formulation and processing of medicines.

Chromatography

Chromatography (from Greek: "chroma" which means color and: "grafein" to write) is the collective term for a family of laboratory techniques for the separation of mixtures. It involves passing a mixture dissolved in a "mobile phase" through a stationary phase, that separates the analyte to be measured from other molecules within the mixture and permits it to be isolated (P.D.Sethi, 2001).

Chromatography may be preparative or analytical. preparative chromatography seeks to separate the components of a combination for further use (and is therefore a form of purification). Analytical chromatography usually operates with smaller amounts of fabric and seeks to measure the relative proportions of analytes in a mixture. the 2 are not reciprocally exclusive.

High-Performance Liquid Chromatography

HPLC is a chromatographical technique used to separate the components in a mixture, to spot every component, and to quantify each element. HPLC is considered an instrumental technique of analytical chemistry. In general, the method involves a liquid sample being passed over a solid adsorbent material packed into a column employing a flow of liquid solvent. HPLC is distinguished from traditional liquid chromatography as a result of operational pressures are significantly higher (50–350 bar), while normal liquid chromatography generally depends on the force of gravity to pass the mobile phase through the column. additionally,

HPLC columns are made with smaller sorbent particles (2–5 micrometer in average particle size). this provides HPLC superior resolving power when separating mixtures, that is why it's a well-liked chromatographic technique.

Types of HPLC techniques:**i. Based on Modes of Chromatography**

- a) Normal Phase chromatography
- b) Reverse Phase chromatography

ii. Based on principle of separation

- a) Adsorption chromatography
- b) Ion exchange chromatography
- c) Ion pair chromatography
- d) Size exclusion chromatography
- e) Affinity chromatography
- f) Chiral phase chromatography

iii. Based on elution technique

- a) Isocratic separation
- b) Gradient separation

iv. Based on the scale of operation

- a) Analytical HPLC.
- b) Preparative HPLC.

Various Methods of Quantitative Analysis In HPLC

Quantification involves the measurement of peak height or peak area. To determine the concentration of a compound, the peak area or height is plotted vs. the concentration of the substance for well resolved peaks, both peak height and area are proportional to the concentration. Five different calibration methods used in quantitative analysis are,

- Calibration by Standards
- Normalized peak are
- External standard addition method
- Internal standard addition method and
- Standard addition method

A typical application of the RI detector is for carbohydrate analysis. Carbohydrates do not adsorb in the UV, do not ionize and although fluorescent derivatives can be made, the procedure is tedious and time consuming.

Equipment's and reagents:

The instruments used in this project are WATERS HPLC 2965 SYSTEM with Auto injector and PDA detector, The software used in the HPLC i.e Empower, micro balance (Sartorius),vacuum filter, Methanol HPLC grade(RANKEM),Acetonitrile HPLC grade (RANKEM),HPLC grade water(RANKEM),Ammonium Acetate.

Drug Profile: Metformin Hydrochloride:

Chemical name of the Metformin Hydrochloride is 1,1-dimethylbiguanide Hydrochloride, systematic IUPAC name was N, N – dimethylimidodicarbonimidic diamide, molecular

formula: $C_4H_{11}N_5HCL$, molecular weight was 165.63g/mol.melting point and pka value is 222-226°C.and 2.8 and 11.5 simultaneously. Category of drug is Anti hyperglycemic agent. The drug soluble in H_2O .Insoluble In Acetone. Ether, Chloroform. The Chemical name of the Gliclazide Glimicron, Diamicron,Nordialexis systematic IUPAC name was -(4-methylbenzenesulfonyl) {octahydrocyclopenta[c]pyrrol- 2-yl}urea molecular formula : $C_{15}H_{21}N_3O_3S$, molecular weight was 323.412 g/mol.melting point and pka value is 180-182 °C..and 5.8 and simultaneously .Category of drug is Anti hyperglycemic agent. The drug partially soluble in H_2O .slightly soluble In acetone,freely soluble in dichloro methane.

Mechanism of action:

Optimized Chromatographic conditions:

Column	:	Phenomenex C_{18} (250×4.6 mm, 5.0 μ m)
Flow rate	:	1.0 ml/min
Detection wavelength	:	240 nm
Injection Volume	:	20 μ l
Temperature	:	ambient
Run time	:	6 min.

It has complex peripheral action in the presence of residual insulin, increasing glucose uptake in striated muscle and inhibiting hepatic glucose output and intestinal glucose absorption.

The Gliclazide mechanism of action is to promote peripheral disposal of glucose by enhancing translocation of glucose transporter to the plasma membrane. It stimulates insulin secretion. It is only effective if β – cells are functional. It blocks ATP sensitive potassium channel in β – cells.

Method development:

Optimized method:

Preparation of Mobile phase:

Prepared a mixture of acetonitrile and buffer in the ratio of 75:25 % v/v and pH of mobile phase was adjusted to 4.7 using dilute orthophosphoric acid.

Figure 1: Chromatogram of optimized method

Observation: Peaks were well separated. Retention time was less and Peak shapes were good

Assay Of Formulation**Procedure:**

Diluent: Acetonitrile: phosphate buffer pH-4.7 (75:25 % v/v), and mixture was adjusted to pH 4.7 using dilute orthophosphoric acid was used as diluent.

Preparation of standard solutions:**Preparation of Standard stock solution of Metformin and Gliclazide:**

Accurately Weighed and transferred 10 mg of Metformin hydrochloride and 1.6 mg of Gliclazide standards into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask and added 3/4th volume of diluent, sonicated for 5 min and make up to the final volume with diluent.(5ml of water and 5ml of acetonitrile is used as diluent).

Preparation of working standard solution of 10 µg Metformin and 1.6 µg Gliclazide:

Working standards solution of Metformin hydrochloride and Gliclazide was prepared by taking 0.1 ml from the above stock solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and made up to 10ml with diluent.(mobile phase used as diluent).

Sample Preparation

Weighed 20 tablets and determined the average weight and crushed to fine powder. Weighed accurately tablet powder equivalent to 10mg of Metformin hydrochloride and 1.6 mg of Gliclazide, transferred into 10 ml volumetric flask, added 3ml of diluent, sonicated for 30 min in cold water and volume was made up to the mark with diluent and filtered. From the filtered solution 0.1 ml was pipetted out into a 10 ml volumetric flask and made up to 10 ml with diluent.

Injected 20 µl of filtered portion of the sample preparation and standard preparation into the chromatograph. The responses for the major peaks were recorded and the content of Metformin hydrochloride and Gliclazide per each tablet was calculated from the following expression.

Acceptance criteria

The percentage purity of Metformin hydrochloride &Gliclazide should be not less than 95 % and not more than 105 %.

Method Validation

Method validation was performed as per the ICH guidelines.

System suitability:**Table 1.: System Suitability Parameters**

	System Suitability Parameters	Results	
		Metformin	Gliclazide
1	Tailing factor(T_f)	1.1	1.0
2	Resolution (R_s)	-	1.902
3	Retention time(R_t)	3.327	4.217
4	Theoretical plates(N)	2745	2684

LINEARITY:**Table 2: Linearity Data for Metformin**

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration (µg/ml)	Area
1	I	5	46403977
2	II	7.5	61615273
3	III	10	77738390
4	IV	12.5	97009942
5	V	15	117406005
Correlation Coefficient			0.993
Slope(m)			8E+06
Intercept			3E+06

Table 3: Linearity data for Gliclazide

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration (µg/ml)	Area
1	I	0.8	1073661
2	II	1.2	1615539
3	III	1.6	2110004
4	IV	2.0	2663926
5	V	2.4	3221109
Correlation Coefficient			0.999
Slope(m)			1E+06
Intercept			-166.2

ACCURACY:

Table 4 : Data for accuracy

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area			Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
	Sample Area	Average	Standard Area				
50 %	61875559	58863051	61615273	7.5	7.16	95.46%	93.99%
	57344958						
	57368637						
100 %	73363978	75040810	77738390	10.0	9.02	90.52%	
	73952024						
	77806427						
150 %	94193197	94599360	97009942	12.5	12.00	96.00%	
	94802442						
	94802452						

Table 5: The accuracy results for Gliclazide

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area			Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
	Sample Area	Average	Standard Area				
50 %	1519742	1731745	1615539	1.2	1.21	100.8	98.53%
	1745168						
	1530326						
100 %	2115926	2112549	2110004	1.6	1.59	99.3	
	2111201						
	2110521						
150 %	3467169	3417900	2663926	2.0	1.91	95.5	
	3393265						
	3393265						

PRECISION:**Method Precision:****Figure 2: Chromatogram of intraday precision****Table 6: intraday precision Data of Metformin and Gliclazide**

S No	METFORMIN		GLICLAZIDE	
	RT(min)	Area (mAU)	RT(min)	Area (mAU)
1	3.337	95689449	4.213	6402565
2	3.341	95313692	4.217	6206876
3	3.339	95027731	4.219	6497946
4	3.335	95099892	4.211	6498919
5	3.341	93820202	4.222	6423171
6	3.339	92061296	4.224	6303218
Avg		94502043.7		6388783
Std Dev		1350898.33		114743.6
% RSD		1.43		1.80

Acceptance Criteria: The RSD should be NMT 2.0 %.¹¹

Method Precision:**Figure 3 : Chromatogram of interday precision:**

Table 7 : Interday Precision Data of Metformin and Gliclazide

S No	METFORMIN		GLICLAZIDE	
	RT (MIN)	Area (mAU)	RT (MIN)	Area (mAU)
1	3.337	95673494	4.213	6421321
2	3.337	94813261	4.219	6341687
3	3.343	95273126	4.217	6218312
4	3.332	93068736	4.211	6431131
5	3.329	93166183	4.214	6318677
6	3.331	94192618	4.215	6437137
Avg		94364570		6361378
Std Dev		1084893		85880.22
% RSD		1.14		1.35

Acceptance Criteria: The RSD should be **eria** NMT 2.0 %.¹¹

Table 8 : Results of Standard & Test Chromatograms for Assay

S.No	PEAK	METFORMIN			GLICLAZIDE		
		RT(min)	AREA (mAU)	% Purity	RT(min)	AREA (mAU)	% Purity
1	Standard	3.380	77738390	99.6 %	4.137	2110004	99.8 %
2	Sample	3.377	77619867	99.2%	4.133	2189969	98.8%

Acceptance criteria:The percentage purity of Metformin hydrochloride & Gliclazide should be not less than 95 % and not more than 105 %.

LIMIT OF DETECTION

The parameter LOD was determined on the basis of response and slope of the regression equation. The Detection Limit (DL) may be expressed as:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \text{ F/S}$$

Where, F = Residual Standard deviation of the response,

S = Slope of the calibration curve.

The LOD for this method was found to be **1.68 µg/ml** and **0.28 µg/ml** for Metformin hydrochloride and Gliclazide respectively.

LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION

The parameter LOQ was determined on the basis of response and slope of the regression equation. The Quantification Limit (QL) may be expressed as:

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \text{ F/S}$$

Where, F = Residual Standard deviation of the response,

S = Slope of the calibration curve.

The LOQ for this method was found to be **4.95 µg/ml** and **0.79 µg/ml** for Metformin and Gliclazide respectively.

CONCLUSION:**Table 9: validation parameters of Metformin and Gliclazide**

PARAMETER	METFORMIN	GLICLAZIDE
Linearity (ug/ml)	5-15 ug/ml	0.8-2.4ug/ml
Correlation Coefficient	0.995	0.999
Slope	8E+06	1E+06
Intercept	3E+06	-166.2
Intra Day Precision	1.43	1.80
Inter Day Precision	1.14	1.35
Mean % Recovery	96.50%	98.53%
Limit Of Detection (ug/ml)	1.68	0.28
Limit Of Quantification (ug/ml)	4.95	0.79
Robustness	Robust	Robust

This developed and validated method for simultaneous analysis of Metformin and Gliclazide in pharmaceutical preparations is very rapid, accurate, and precise. The method was successfully applied for determination of MET and GLI in its Bulk and Pharmaceutical dosage form. The proposed method was simple and did not involve laborious time-consuming sample preparation. Moreover it has advantages of low costs of reagents used, short run time and the possibility of analysis of a large number of samples. Hence this method can be conveniently used for routine analysis and quality control of pharmaceutical preparations containing these drugs either as such or in combination.

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